

Influence of weather factors on light trap catches of yellow stem borer (YSB)

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Light trap catches of YSB were recorded for a year (1988-89) using three light traps: a local bamboo light trap with an ordinary incandescent 40-watt bulb (LBL-T 40 W) and two modified Robinson light traps, one with a 125-watt mercury vapor lamp (MRL-T 125 W) and the other with a 200-watt incandescent bulb (MRL-T 200 W). Traps were

Multiple regression between YSB catches in different light traps and weather parameters^a at RRS, Tirur.

Trap	Multiple regression equation	R ²
LBL-T 40 W	93.07197 + 0.05877x ₁ - 0.86273x ₂ - 0.31734x ₃ - 0.83071x ₄	0.34962
MRL-T 125 W	88.30018 - 1.06939x ₁ - 0.06741x ₂ - 0.56557x ₃ - 0.50919x ₄	0.33739
MRL-T 200 W	201.77216 - 1.69501x ₁ - 0.89709x ₂ - 0.92290x ₃ - 1.28137x ₄	0.30677
LBL-T 40 W + MRL-T 125 W + MRL-T 200 W	356.64844 - 2.18550x ₁ - 1.98679x ₂ - 1.86689x ₃ - 2.46711x ₄	0.32607

^ax₁ = maximum temperature, x₂ = minimum temperature, x₃ = rainfall, x₄ = relative humidity.

installed 100 m apart at the Rice Research Station (RRS), Tirur.

Multiple regression analysis was used to study the influence of weather elements on YSB catches. Mean weather parameters for the corresponding week were compared with light trap catches.

The regression equation explained 35% of the variation in LBL-T 40 W, 33.7% in MRL-T 125 W, and 30.7% in MRL-T 200 W, and 32.6% in the three traps collectively (see table). Weather factors did not significantly contribute to the trap catches, irrespective of light trap design. □

Integrated pest management—other pests

Use of ducks to control golden apple snail *Ampullarius (Pomacea) canaliculata* in irrigated rice

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The golden apple snail was introduced in the Philippines as a source of food and income in the early 1980s. It spread into rice and now infests 400,000 ha. Farmers controlled the pest with chemical molluscicides until use was suspended because of safety and environmental concerns.

Some Filipino farmers have used ducks (an important income source) to control the golden apple snail in rice. But no previous studies had documented the efficacy of ducks in suppressing snails or the stocking density needed for good results.

We conducted a field experiment on the IRRI farm to determine how many ducks are needed to control snails in 1 ha of irrigated rice during the dry season (May 1991). Snails were up to 3 cm in diameter and were not fully grown.

The 10- × 10-m experimental plots were irrigated. Snails were counted 2 d later in five 1-m quadrats to estimate populations. Ducks (0, 2, 4, 8, 16, and 32/plot) were then introduced.

Treatments were replicated five times. Ducks remained in the plots for 2 d (8 h/d) and were then removed. Rice variety IR72 (12 d old) was transplanted the next day.

Snail populations were estimated again for each plot at 7 d after transplant-

ing using the same procedure. Rice was examined for snail damage.

Two ducks/plot (200/ha) significantly reduced both the snail population (Table 1) and damage to rice, with four or more per plot increasing effectiveness (Table 2). Results show that ducks are a potential alternative to chemical molluscicides in controlling the golden apple snail. □

Table 1. Efficiency of different duck densities in reducing snail populations in irrigated rice. IRRI, May 1991.

Duck density/plot	Snail control (%) in 7 d
0	13.4 b
2	89.2 a
4	77.2 a
8	91.4 a
16	97.2 a
32	95.8 a

^aMeans with a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test (CV = 29%).

Table 2. Snail damage in irrigated rice at 7 d after transplanting with different densities of ducks, IRRI, May 1991.

Duck density/plot	Snail-damaged rice hills ^a (no./100 m ²)
0	17.4 c
2	8.2 bc
4	6.6 b
8	5.2 b
16	2.0 a
32	4.0 b

^aMeans with a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with upland rice in Sitiung, West Sumatra, Indonesia

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We conducted a preliminary survey to identify the major plant parasitic

nematodes in upland rice in Sitiung. Deforestation and opening agricultural land at the site began 15 yr ago; upland rice has been cultivated for 13 yr.

We collected 141 soil and root samples of a second upland rice crop, 1 yr after deforestation, at the SARIF experimental station in Sitiung (new fields = NF), and of 13-yr-old continuously cropped upland ricefields (old fields = OF). The third set was from

farmers' fields where upland rice has been grown for 1–13 yr (farmers' fields = FF).

Eight plant parasitic nematode genera were observed: *Criconebella*, *Helicotylenchus*, *Hoplolaimus*, *Meloidogyne*, *Pratylenchus*, *Rotylenchulus*, *Trychodorus*, and *Xiphinema*.

Frequency (% of samples containing the genera) and abundance (log of the average number per dm³ of soil and g of root) were calculated in each field type for the four most important genera: *Criconebella*, *Meloidogyne*, *Pratylenchus*, and *Xiphinema* (see figure).

Nematodes are considered potentially economically important when detected in >30% of surveyed fields. Nematodes are considered crop parasites when 200 individuals are recovered per dm³ of soil (abundance = 2.3) or an average of more than 20 individuals are recovered from 1 g of root (abundance = 1.3).

Hoplolaimus, *Rotylenchulus*, and *Trychodorus* were detected in only 1, 1, and 3 samples, respectively, indicating they are not important upland rice parasites in Sitiung. Population densities of *Helicotylenchus* were low in 13% of the samples.

High population densities of the four most important nematodes were observed in the rhizosphere and roots of upland rice, indicating they are parasites.

The prevalent genus of plant parasitic nematode (*Pratylenchus*) in Sitiung was found in 66% of the samples. Duration of rice cultivation affected its occurrence, with detection in 39% of NF and 100% of OF.

Criconebella was detected in 43% of OF. High population densities of *Meloidogyne* were in a few locations

Frequency and abundance per dm³ of soil and g of root of the major plant parasitic nematodes associated with upland rice in Sitiung, Sumatra, Indonesia. Vertical line = when nematode genera are considered frequent (>30%). Horizontal line = when abundance index >2.3 in soil and 1.3 in roots.

(16%). *Xiphinema* was frequently detected in NF (31%), but not in OF (7%). Population with the highest frequency appears to shift from *Xiphinema* to *Pratylenchus* with increased years of cultivation.

Pratylenchus seems to be the main concern, but methods used to control it must not favor buildup of *Meloidogyne* and *Criconebella* populations. □

Farming systems

Rice - fish farming system for Hunan, China

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About 87,000 ha were devoted to rice - fish farming in Hunan Province in 1990. We evaluated the suitability and economics of the rice - fish system in 1990-91.

Soil was Quaternary period red earth with pH 6.1, 0.8% organic C, and 140.2, 38, and 127 ppm available N, P, and K, respectively.

The multiple system experiment consisted of the three dominant patterns in Hunan and was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Varieties used were early rice Wei You 35, late rice Wei You 64, and rape variety Xiang 11.

Rice - azolla - rape had the highest rice yield (Table 1), but the lowest